

METHODS AND MEANS OF BLOCKING BOTNETS BASED ON INTELLIGENT DATA ANALYSIS

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Abstract: In this paper, Using a massive number of coordinated and distributed machines, botnets have become one of the most sophisticated cyber threats. However, software defined networking leads to more effective mitigation approaches by providing a flexible and dynamic way to control the network. Existing botnet detection approaches fail to detect unknown botnet threats and are time consuming. Facing these shortcomings motivates us to employ honeypots as a competent solution. We propose a novel blocking approach that uses honeypots to detect and efficiently prevent botnet propagation in software defined networks. This approach identifies the relationship among botnet members and intelligently blocks them. We also design and implement a deception system based on our blocking approach with two goals: reducing the botnet infection rate and wasting the adversary's time. Experimental results, which are based on a real malware, show that our proposed system compared with current blocking approaches can reduce the infection rate up to 25% and increase the adversary's wasted time by a factor of four. Our system also provides a satisfactory detection performance.

Keywords: Botnet detection, Intelligent blocking, Network security, Cyber deception, computer security.

Introduction: Machine learning and statistical analysis methods have their own disadvantages (Barocas et al.,2020; Team 2021). The performance of machine learning methods depends on the dataset that has been used for training. Statistical analysis is also dependent upon the chosen features. The number of devices

connected to Internet to ex-change data is exploding in the recent years. Due to variety and heterogeneity of these devices and lack of a comprehensive security plan, most of them are vulnerable to cyber threats. These vulnerabilities have been exploited by the attackers to compromise the systems. The most serious and sophisticated threats are launched by botnets. Botnets are massive groups of coordinated malicious machines performing distributed attacks against the targeted systems. We also propose a deception system which has been designed for our approach with two goals: (1) reducing host infection and (2) wasting attacker’s time. Our main contributions are summarized as follows:

- Introducing a novel intelligent blocking approach
 - that can identify the relationship among botnet members in SDN and prevent their propagation.
- Design and implementation of a deception system
 - based on our intelligent blocking approach.
- Reducing the host infection rate up to 25% and
 - increasing adversary’s wasted time up to a factor of four in comparison with previous works, shown
 - through experimental results.
- Proposing a novel SDN-based system using decep-
 - definition techniques and honeypots to detect botnets.
- Proposing a system architecture that uses the stan-
 - OpenFlow structure and can be implemented in any general SDN environment.

Materials: To addresses these challenges, in this paper we introduce an intelligent blocking approach that is able to detect botnets in the early stages of their lifecycle and to prevent their propagation in SDN.

Methods: To better show the experimental results, we compare our intelligent blocking approach with normal blocking approach used in the previous works. The detected bots are blocked in normal blocking approach, but the undetected ones are still able to in- form the loaders (which are not still detected) about the vulnerabilities. This is why the infection rate is not zero in normal blocking approach.

As we expected, in all experiments the number of infected hosts is nearly zero in intelligent blocking approach. In most of the experiments the infection rate is significantly reduced comparing with normal blocking approach. The infection rate is reduced up to 25% and it confirms that our intelligent approach achieved its first goal. In all experiments with sequential scanning strategy no hosts are infected. This is due to the mechanism of creating virtual topologies with high address distance. Another notable point is that the infection rate in heavy conditions is more reduced than in light conditions.

Results: Two metrics can determine how much our proposed system achieves its goals: the number of infected hosts and the adversary’s wasted time. There are also some metrics to measure the performance of our system. In the following, the results of evaluating different experiments with these metrics are presented.

Conclusion: In this paper we introduced a novel intelligent blocking approach in SDN to detect and prevent botnets propagation. We used honeypots and deception techniques for this approach to overcome the previous works shortcomings. We proposed a system based on this approach with two design goals: reducing the number of infected hosts and wasting adversary’s time. The main components of our proposed system are topology deceiver, decoy manager, and SDN controller. Topology deceiver creates a virtual topology to hide the real one and place the fake hosts in the network. The decoy manager detects loaders by identifying the relationship among different botnet members. Finally, the SDN controller intelligently blocks the detected loaders. We evaluate different aspects of our system. The experimental results show that our intelligent blocking approach can decrease the number of infected hosts by 10% and increase the adversary’s wasted time by a factor of four. As future work, we plan to extend our proposed system to contain distributed decoy managers. It helps the system reduce the network traffic load on centralized decoy manager and work more efficient in largescale networks.

A botnet is a network of infected machines which are compromised by a malicious program that causes them to perform additional tasks without their owners knowledge. These exploited machines are called bots and the adversary who controls

them is called botmaster. Botmaster needs a communication channel to remotely control the bots. Typically, a central command and control server is employed for this purpose. The bots join a specific channel on command and control server to receive adversary's commands. When an activator is interacting with a decoy, if the number of its previous attempts is less than a threshold (lower t), that decoy rejects the current attempt. We also define another threshold, called upper t , to make sure that the activator gets successful response after a maximum number of failed attempts. If the number of previous attempts goes higher than upper t , the decoy will accept the attempt. If the number of previous attempts is between lower t and upper t , the current attempt is successful with a probability of bootnet. We now explain how credentials help decoy manager to find the loader. If a bot uses a specific credential to login a decoy and another node uses exactly the same credential in its first attempt to that decoy, the second node may be a loader. Because the probability of the first attempt to be successful is very low. Example clarifies how decoy manager detects the loaders using credentials. There is also another point to consider. An adversary, who knows the deception strategy of our system, can evade intelligent blocking approach. The adversary may change the loaders operation and make them try some invalid login pairs before the valid one. This may cause our system believe that the loader is a normal scanner. Changing the behaviour of the loader to perform additional probes, wastes adversary's resource and time, but brings a countermeasure. So we plan to improve our proposed approach to cover this aspect

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